

101132933 – AD-RIDDLE

Real-World Implementation, Deployment and Validation of Early Detection Tools and Lifestyle Enhancement

WP8 – Communications, Public Involvement, and Outreach

D8.2 Communication and Dissemination Strategy

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DEFINITIONS

Participants of the AD-RIDDLE Consortium are referred to herein according to the following codes:

RS: Region Stockholm, Karolinska Universitetssjukhuset - Sweden (**The Coordinator**)

KI: Karolinska Institutet, Department of Neurobiology, Care Sciences and Society - Sweden

FBHI: Stiftelsen Fingers Brain Health Institute - Sweden

UGOT: Goeteborgs Universitet - Sweden

ULUND: Lunds Universitet - Sweden

UEF: Itäلتältä-suomen Yliopisto, University of Eastern Finland - Finland

VUMC: Stichting VUmc - The Netherlands

UM: Universiteit Maastricht - The Netherlands

BBRC: Fundació Barcelonabeta Brain Research Center - Spain

SYNAPSE: Synapse Research Management Partners S.L - Spain

AE: Alzheimer Europe - Luxembourg

ADI: Alzheimer’s Disease International – United States

UNIPG: Universita Degli Studi di Perugia - Italy

GV: Gates Ventures LLC – United States (**The Co-Coordinator**)

DAC: Davos Alzheimer’s Collaborative - Switzerland

COMBINOSTICS: Combinostics Oy - Finland

Fujirebio: Fujirebio Europe NV - Belgium

SARD: Sanofi-Aventis Recherche & Development - France

C2N: C2N Diagnostics LLC – United States

neotiv GmbH: Neotiv GmbH - Germany

CCL: Cambridge Cognition Limited – United Kingdom

ULEIC: University of Leicester – United Kingdom

ICL: Imperial College of Science, Technology and medicine - United Kingdom

NICE: National Institute for Health and Care Excellence- United Kingdom

Grant agreement

The agreement signed between the beneficiaries and the IHI for the undertaking of the AD-RIDDLE project (101132933).

Project

The sum of all activities carried out in the framework of the Grant Agreement.

Consortium

The AD-RIDDLE Consortium, comprising the above-mentioned legal entities.

Consortium agreement

Agreement concluded amongst AD-RIDDLE participants for the implementation of the Grant Agreement. Such an agreement shall not affect the parties’ obligations to the Community and/or to one another arising from the Grant Agreement.

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Deliverable 8.2 (D8.2) describes the Initial Communication and Dissemination Strategy for AD-RIDDLE. As a living document, it will be regularly updated throughout the project duration, to ensure communication and activities meet evolving strategic and operational needs.

D8.2 outlines the methods, channels, tools and activities that will be used to meet the IHI requirements for effective communication and dissemination, thereby maximising the impact of AD-RIDDLE. Building on a stakeholder mapping and analysis exercise, D8.2 identifies communication objectives, target audiences and anticipated timelines for activities, providing a communications roadmap for AD-RIDDLE. It lays out the visual identity and messaging strategy of AD-RIDDLE, to ensure a consistent, professional approach to communications across the project. D8.2 also identifies a series of metrics and indicators, which will be used to monitor, record and adapt communication activities across the project funding period. Finally, D8.2 introduces the AD-RIDDLE Public Awareness Strategy (D8.3), which will be published in month 24 of the project, building on the present deliverable. AD-RIDDLE communications activities will be reported at M30 and M60, identifying areas of the Strategy that have been amended or adapted.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Effective communication and dissemination are important contributors to research impact. To influence wider changes in thinking, behaviour or policy, research must be disseminated to audiences within and beyond the immediate field of research. As well as increasing visibility, this promotes the engagement of key societal stakeholders, paving the way towards adoption and implementation of research innovations.

Alzheimer’s disease (AD) affects an estimated 10 million people in Europe, with numbers expected to double by 2050. Ensuring impact from research is particularly important for the AD community, with few therapeutic options available, long waits for diagnosis, and challenges accessing support and care. The Innovative Health Initiative (IHI) recognises the importance of effective communication to maximise research impact, clearly stating in its Guide for IHI project communications¹ that beneficiaries “*must promote the project and its results... in a coherent and strategic way.*” Communications should also include the public policy perspective, by addressing impact, exploitation and cooperation. Consequently, research projects have an obligation to communicate widely on their activities, and to disseminate project findings to audiences in an open and timely manner.

Work package 8 (WP8) is designed to support the communication activities of project partners, and to coordinate communication and dissemination through project-specific channels. The specific goals of WP8 are:

- To achieve wide outreach and raise awareness of AD-RIDDLE in key audiences, through project-specific communication activities, as well as activities that leverage partner channels,
- To set up and manage a Patient and Public Advisory Group for AD-RIDDLE, composed of people with or at-risk of dementia, mild cognitive impairment, and their carers or family members²; and
- To co-develop a public awareness strategy and organise awareness campaigns that will effectively target end users (at-risk individuals, citizens, healthcare professionals), increase awareness of positive brain health practices, and support implementation and adoption of the AD-RIDDLE toolkit

D8.2 (Communication and Dissemination Strategy) is the first deliverable report for WP8. D8.2 is a living document that outlines the strategies, methods, channels, tools and activities that will be used to meet the IHI requirements for effective communication and dissemination, thereby maximising the impact of AD-RIDDLE. D8.2 identifies communication objectives, target audiences and anticipated timelines for activities, providing a communications roadmap for AD-RIDDLE. It lays out the visual identity and messaging strategy of AD-RIDDLE, to ensure a consistent, professional

¹ Communications guide for IHI projects: <https://www.ihl.europa.eu/resources-projects/project-communications>

² The AD-RIDDLE DoA is being amended to move the task connected this goal to WP7

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approach to communications across the project. The strategy will remain a living document throughout the duration of AD-RIDDLE and will be adapted as the project evolves.

AD-RIDDLE project outline

AD-RIDDLE aims to enhance the detection, diagnosis, prevention and treatment of Alzheimer’s disease, speeding up patient access to healthcare providers and precision medicine.

As the global population ages, the number of people with dementia is forecasted to grow from over 57 million today to 153 million by 2050. Recent advances in blood-based biomarkers, digital cognitive tests, disease-modifying therapies and multidomain interventions provide new opportunities for clinical management and care. However, there is a pressing need for these innovations to be implemented at scale, across geographical regions and healthcare settings.

To enhance access to these innovative diagnostics and treatments, AD-RIDDLE is building a scalable, modular toolbox platform to provide support at all stages of the clinical pathway. The toolbox components include a digital community engagement portal with self-guided assessment tools, a suite of validated digital cognitive assessments and blood-based biomarker tests, and a decision support toolkit to help clinicians match patients with the right interventions, at the right time.

The 24 partners in the AD-RIDDLE interdisciplinary consortium will develop and test the AD-RIDDLE toolbox platform and its components individually and in combination in six European countries, paving the way for wider deployment in real-world clinical settings. Ultimately, AD-RIDDLE will enable better disease detection, intervention and prevention, improving outcomes for patients and their families, and reducing costs for healthcare systems.

1.1 Stakeholder map

The first step of an effective communication strategy is to **identify** and **understand** the stakeholders who will be the target audiences for communication and dissemination at different points in a given research project. To identify key stakeholders for AD-RIDDLE, we undertook an initial stakeholder mapping exercise, based on an analysis of the AD-RIDDLE Description of Action (DoA). This mapping exercise identified three categories of stakeholders, defined by their proximity and interaction with the AD-RIDDLE toolbox platform (see **Fig. 1** below):

- **Primary stakeholders/audiences:** groups that will directly interact with the AD-RIDDLE toolbox platform, or which can directly impact the uptake and design of the platform
- **Secondary stakeholders/audiences:** groups that may benefit from, or provide funding for AD-RIDDLE, and have an interest in adoption of its toolbox platform
- **Tertiary stakeholders/audiences:** groups that could collaborate with, champion, or raise awareness of AD-RIDDLE in key audiences

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Fig.1. AD-RIDDLE stakeholder map. Diagram illustrating the primary, secondary and tertiary stakeholders for AD-RIDDLE

Primary, secondary and tertiary stakeholders are further classified into the following groups:

Primary Stakeholders/Audiences

- **Primary End Users:** groups that are expected to interact directly with the AD-RIDDLE toolbox platform (healthcare providers, e.g. neurologists, geriatricians, old age psychiatrists, general practitioners/GPs; patients and older adults with cognitive complaints; caregivers)
- **Secondary End Users:** groups that can directly impact the adoption and design of the AD-RIDDLE toolbox platform (e.g. memory clinics & primary care clinics; technology and test developers) or who will use the outputs from AD-RIDDLE (e.g. regulators or health technology assessment/HTA using evidence from the platform)

Secondary Stakeholders/Audiences

- **Beneficiaries:** groups that benefit from AD-RIDDLE tools and outputs (e.g. healthcare systems) and can influence adoption
- **Funders:** groups providing funding for AD-RIDDLE currently, or in the future (e.g. IHI, national payers, insurance companies); have an interest in adoption

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Tertiary Stakeholders/Audiences

- **Collaborators:** groups or individuals that could collaborate with AD-RIDDLE or its partners (e.g AD researchers and research institutions; SMEs and other technology developers)
- **Peers:** individuals and organisations that can champion AD-RIDDLE (e.g. key opinion leaders/KOLs, Professional societies, research initiatives with aligned objectives)
- **Amplifiers:** groups that can amplify AD-RIDDLE’s messages, expanding reach (e.g. online & print media, journalists)

Next, we classified the different stakeholder groups according to the level of interest they have in AD-RIDDLE, and the amount of influence or power they have over the adoption of the AD-RIDDLE toolbox platform (**Fig. 2** below). This initial classification helps inform the cadence, intensity and mode of communication with the stakeholder groups.

Fig.2 AD-RIDDLE stakeholder matrix. Interest-Influence classification of AD-RIDDLE audiences and stakeholders

- **Group 1** has the highest interest and influence on AD-RIDDLE, and includes priority audiences for AD-RIDDLE to *engage regularly and manage closely*: clinicians, older adults, patients & carers, memory clinics & primary care clinics, technology & test developers.
- **Group 2** includes audiences which should be kept *regularly informed*, who have a strong interest in AD-RIDDLE, but lower power to influence adoption: the AD research community, professional societies, patient organisations, industry, and the science media.

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- **Group 3**, conversely, includes audiences with high power to influence adoption of AD-RIDDLE, but lower specific interest in the project. These audiences should be *engaged periodically*: healthcare systems, policymakers, HTA & payers, and research funders.
- **Group 4** includes audiences with low interest in AD-RIDDLE, who also have low relative influence on adoption, to *inform occasionally*: key opinion leaders, the general public, and journalists.

1.2 Audience analysis & insights

Having mapped and classified the key stakeholders/audiences for AD-RIDDLE, we undertook an interview-based analysis to understand areas of interest in AD-RIDDLE for different stakeholders, as well as their potential communication needs. This work was organised by WP8 partners, GV. Interviews were conducted with AD-RIDDLE consortium stakeholders representing some of the groups identified in the mapping exercise (in particular: clinicians, AD researchers, industry representatives, patient organisations).

This exercise will be expanded as the project progresses, incorporating insights from additional stakeholder groups, allowing us to adapt and refine our communication approaches. The table below details the insights from an initial analysis of four key AD-RIDDLE audiences: clinicians; patients and carers (Group 1); the AD research community (Group 2); and policymakers (Group 3).

Audience	Interest in AD-RIDDLE	Communication needs
Clinicians	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Opportunities to gain efficiency in patient treatment and care pipeline • Access to an array of validated tests and tools to enable improved diagnosis • Decision support for early AD detection, treatment and care, including guidance on patient-doctor communications • Resources and supporting data for lifestyle recommendations and therapeutic interventions • Resources that can support patients and their caregivers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clear communications on how the AD-RIDDLE platform will work and who is involved in the project • Clear communications on the scientific and clinical evidence base for the platform and its components, including digital cognitive assessments, blood-based biomarker tests, algorithms and therapeutic/preventative interventions • Regular updates about AD-RIDDLE to understand the timing of platform roll-out, and to stay engaged before the platform launches • Onboarding materials for seamless use and access to AD-RIDDLE platform, potentially including clinical training and guidance

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Patients & carers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Access to validated and effective self-assessment tools • Faster, easier and more regular access to clinicians, for a timely diagnosis and enhanced care • Removal of barriers to entry and broadened patient access to treatment and interventions • Holistic, personalised post-diagnostic support, with clear signposting, guidance and access to local services • Education and informative resources about cognitive impairment and dementia • Education and informative resources about lifestyle interventions and therapeutic options 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understanding of how the AD-RIDDLE platform will work and who is involved in the project • Accessible, lay communications on the science behind AD-RIDDLE and the components of the toolbox platform • Accessible information and communications materials about cognitive impairment, dementia, lifestyle interventions and therapeutic options • Updates about key AD-RIDDLE milestones, to understand the timing of platform roll-out, and how to access the platform once it launches
AD researchers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clarity on how AD-RIDDLE will work, its value to the AD community, and who is involved in the project • Access to AD-RIDDLE platform components (e.g. digital cognitive assessments, blood-based biomarker tests or predictive algorithms) for use in their own studies • Access to datasets contributed to, or generated by AD-RIDDLE, which cover a diverse and broad population of people with, or at risk of AD • Collaborative engagement with the AD-RIDDLE project and/or its partners 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clear communications on how the AD-RIDDLE platform will work and who is involved in the project • Clear communications on the scientific evidence base for the platform and its components • Regular updates about AD-RIDDLE to understand the timing and availability of datasets and other project resources • Informational materials on how to access AD-RIDDLE datasets & other resources; and opportunities for collaborative engagement
Policymakers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clarity on how AD-RIDDLE will work, its potential impact on AD at a population and individual level, and who is involved in the project • Evidence-based information on lifestyle recommendations and therapeutic interventions, including details of cost:effectiveness • Opportunities for greater efficiency and efficacy of patient treatment and care 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clear communications on how the AD-RIDDLE platform will work and who is involved in the project • Clear communications on the evidence base for the platform and its components, including scientific & health economic evidence • Informational materials and communications about the prevalence and impact of

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- | | |
|---|---|
| <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Real-world outcomes of early detection, timely diagnosis, lifestyle and other therapeutic interventions • Public health measures to improve dementia detection, prevention and treatment | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • cognitive impairment and dementia • Informational materials and communications about the value and potential for lifestyle interventions & personalised medicine • Regular updates on AD-RIDDLE platform development and roll-out |
|---|---|

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2. COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION PLAN

2.1 Communication objectives

Our initial stakeholder mapping and analysis exercise focused on four key audiences/stakeholder groups, identifying areas of interest in AD-RIDDLE, as well as associated communication needs (see previous section).

Based on this exercise, we have identified five communication objectives for AD-RIDDLE:

Throughout the project duration, communications partners in WP8 will pro-actively engage with the project leadership team and wider consortium to ensure the communication objectives remain aligned with the evolving operational objectives, challenges and priorities of AD-RIDDLE. By consistently supporting external communications of AD-RIDDLE partners, this will help align messaging and audience engagement strategies across the project.

2.2 Audiences

In this section, we list the key audiences identified through our stakeholder mapping and analysis exercise, focusing on the three priority groups with greatest influence on, and interest in AD-RIDDLE

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(see Fig. 2). The table below provides brief descriptions of each audience, to inform and guide the design of communication and dissemination activities.

AUDIENCE PRIORITY	AUDIENCE	AUDIENCE CHARACTERISTICS
Group 1 Direct & indirect end users of AD-RIDDLE engage frequently	<i>Clinicians</i>	Doctors and healthcare professionals in memory clinics and primary care settings, who deal with people who have or may be at risk of AD. Specialities include neurology, psychiatry, geriatrics, neuroradiology, nuclear medicine and neuropsychology. Management of people with or at risk of AD varies across European countries, with different specialities more or less implicated in diagnosis, treatment and care.
	<i>Patients & carers</i>	People living with cognitive impairment or dementia. The majority of these individuals will be older adults, although early-onset AD can affect people at younger ages. Peoples' lived experience of AD varies widely, depending on several factors including the type and stage of disease, social and cultural environment and personality. Carers include people who provide direct care for people with AD, such as family members, partners or friends.
	<i>Technology & test developers</i>	Companies or organisations developing digital or fluid biomarker tests, or algorithms, to enhance the detection, diagnosis or prognosis of AD. Companies and organisations may be in the public or private sector, operating at different scales, with products and innovations that may be at varying stages of development for different regions or indications.
Group 2 Collaborators and peers of AD-RIDDLE inform frequently	<i>AD researchers</i>	Researchers working on AD, either directly with patients or research participants, or using clinical data and samples. This is a diverse group that may include clinicians (e.g. neurologists, psychiatrists, geriatricians) or non-clinical researchers (e.g. epidemiologists, data scientists) addressing a wide range of research questions and areas, in the private or public sector. They may also be at a range of career stages, and may combine their research activities with clinical activities.
	<i>Professional societies</i>	Networks that bring together researchers, sites or institutions with a shared interest or goal, which may act as gatekeepers to different communities of practice. Examples include the European Alzheimer's Disease Consortium (EADC) and European Academy of Neurology (EAN). These networks may vary in size and scope, with different organisational structures.
	<i>Patient organisations</i>	Organisations that represent and advocate for people with Alzheimer's disease and other dementias. Organisations may operate within different regions, and may provide different services and support to people with AD and their carers. Examples of umbrella patient organisations include Alzheimer Europe and Alzheimer's Disease International, which can act as gatekeepers to patient networks.
Group 3 Beneficiaries & funders of AD-RIDDLE	<i>Healthcare systems</i>	A system comprising all organisations, people and resources that deliver health care services to meet the health needs of target populations. The structure of healthcare systems varies between countries and is primarily organised at national level, including planning and commissioning of healthcare services

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engage periodically	and infrastructures, including procurement of clinical tests & treatments.
<i>Policy makers</i>	Policy makers working in a wide variety of roles and areas at the European Institutions (e.g. European Parliament, European Commission) and/or national policy makers working in departments with a health, research or care remit.
<i>HTA & payers</i>	Health Technology Assessment bodies are organisations that make decisions about funding for new medicines or technologies within national health systems, based on parameters such as cost-effectiveness, efficacy and value to patients. Payers are commercial, private and government/public bodies that control the reimbursement of health services, treatments and care. The payer landscape varies widely across Europe, with different systems (e.g. single-payer, co-insurance) in different countries.
<i>Research funders</i>	Organisations that provide funding for research and innovation projects nationally, at European level, or globally. Funding streams and calls may have specific remits and requirements, with funds derived from public or private resources. Examples of research funders include the EU Joint Programme for Neurodegenerative Disease Research (JPND), Horizon Europe, the UK Medical Research Council and the Alzheimer’s Drug Discovery Foundation.

2.3 Messaging

Clear and consistent messaging plays a pivotal role in establishing a project’s identity to external audiences, forming a solid foundation to build awareness, engagement and impact. Below, we identify several high-level messages targeted at key AD-RIDDLE audiences (clinicians, patients, AD researchers and policymakers).

The messages have been informed by our stakeholder analysis exercise and aim to meet their communication needs (listed in section 1.2) aligned with the communication goals of the project (listed in section 2.1). The messages may evolve over time as the project progresses, and will be revisited regularly to ensure consistent alignment with communication objectives and operational goals of AD-RIDDLE, as relevant.

Audience	Priority Messages to Communicate
Clinicians	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>AD-RIDDLE allows for timely and tailored AD patient intervention and better patient management</i> • <i>AD-RIDDLE assists in early risk and disease detection through digital screening, cognitive testing, and blood-based biomarkers</i> • <i>AD-RIDDLE provides validation of blood-based biomarkers and digital cognitive assessments for AD patients</i> • <i>AD-RIDDLE is highly accessible due to digital screening and testing, removing barriers to entry like travel for assessments</i> • <i>AD-RIDDLE supports clinical decision-making, matching patients with the right treatments, at the right time.</i>

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Patients & caregivers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>AD-RIDDLE empowers me to take action on behalf of my cognitive health</i> • <i>AD-RIDDLE gives me tangible options for addressing my cognitive health, from referring me to a doctor to giving me things I can do in my life to slow cognitive decline</i> • <i>AD-RIDDLE takes my diagnosis and individual health history into account to give me a plan that’s personalised and actionable</i> • <i>AD-RIDDLE provides me with reliable information about cognitive impairment, testing, treatment and care options</i>
AD researchers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>AD-RIDDLE represents an important opportunity for cross-sector progress, thanks to its multi-disciplinary partners, and ability to test, apply, and refine across perspectives with real-world applications</i> • <i>AD-RIDDLE will have high-quality patient data because of broad and diverse patient participation</i> • <i>AD-RIDDLE will generate real-world evidence of treatment implementation and lifestyle interventions in different settings and with diverse patients</i> • <i>AD-RIDDLE will help unlock new insights and advance AD research, thanks to new datasets, cross-sector collaboration, more diverse patient participation, and increased availability of innovative tests and interventions</i>
Policymakers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>AD-RIDDLE represents an important opportunity for cross-sector progress, thanks to its multi-disciplinary partners, and ability to test, apply, and refine across perspectives with real-world applications</i> • <i>AD-RIDDLE will unlock efficiencies for AD diagnosis and treatment, removing barriers to entry that slow down patient access to doctors, and precision medicine such as treatments and lifestyle interventions</i> • <i>AD-RIDDLE will allow for timely and tailored options for patients who are worried about their cognitive health, accelerating diagnosis and improving outcomes for patients and healthcare systems</i> • <i>AD-RIDDLE will provide patients and their families with trustworthy, personalised, and actionable resources about AD, empowering them to manage their cognitive health in collaboration with healthcare providers</i>

2.4 Tools and channels

Effective communication and dissemination of AD-RIDDLE’s achievements require the use of **various tools, channels and materials** to reach the identified audiences (see section 2.2). The AD-RIDDLE consortium has started to design and produce several tools and channels needed to implement the communication plan. This section outlines the key tools and channels (summarised in the table below) that will be utilised throughout the project, with the **flexibility** to adapt or develop new tools as needed.

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Tool & Channel	Focus	Target stakeholder	Frequency
Logo & visual identity	Branding to ensure consistent visual representation	All	Continuous
Project templates	Providing a consistent format for communication activities	All	Continuous
Information sheets, pitch deck and infographics	Providing accessible information for awareness by simplifying high-level information about AD-RIDDLE into visual formats	All (tailored)	As needed
Website	Central hub for information, news and resources	All	Continuous
Social media channels	Increasing visibility of the project, engaging with the community, driving traffic to the project website	All	Weekly
Newsletter	Highlighting progress and key findings	All	Quarterly
Press release	Sharing major achievements and milestones widely	All	As needed (e.g., major updates or findings)
Participation in conferences or events	Raising awareness of the project, presenting findings, networking	Researchers, Healthcare Providers, Policymakers, Dementia community	Bi-annually
Scientific Papers	Sharing findings	Researchers, Healthcare Providers	As findings/outputs are available
AE & ADI channels	Reaching a broader audience, building community support	Researchers, Policy Makers, Dementia community	Monthly

2.4.1 Logo & visual identity

The AD-RIDDLE logo serves as a visual identity for the project and will be prominently displayed on all communication materials. This includes brochures, leaflets, posters, presentations and digital content. The AD-RIDDLE logo will also be used in conjunction with the IHI JU logo, the EU emblem and the logos of COCIR, EFPIA, EuropaBio, MedTech Europe and Vaccines Europe to acknowledge funding and support.

The AD-RIDDLE logo was developed at the very beginning of the project to ensure a **unified image** from the outset. The logotype consists of a modern wordmark interwoven with a Light Red line that represents the journey towards better detection, diagnosis and treatment of Alzheimer’s disease. It comes in several versions and colours (Fig.3), including with and without a descriptor, to ensure appropriate use in diverse communication scenarios. The primary colours used in the logo are Dark

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Blue, Light Red, Light Blue and White. The logotype and colours are approved for use across all communications online and in print.

The AD-RIDDLE logo and visual identity elements are summarised in an identity style guide, providing comprehensive instructions on the proper use of the logo, including specifications on the colour palette and typography. The identity style guide is accessible to all consortium members via the internal SharePoint platform. Adherence to these guidelines ensures that all project-related materials reflect a unified and recognisable brand image.

Fig.3. AD-RIDDLE logos

2.4.2 Templates

To ensure **consistency and brand coherence** across all communications, a series of unified templates have been developed. These templates are designed based on the visual identity of the AD-RIDDLE project and aim to provide both functionality and alignment with the project's branding. Each template incorporates the AD-RIDDLE logo, project colours and approved fonts.

The templates currently available are listed below and are available for the Consortium members via the internal SharePoint platform.

- **Presentation templates:** Standardised slides for use in conferences and internal meetings.
- **Document templates:** These include templates for various types of Word documents such as deliverables, letters, meeting agendas and press releases.
- **Quote card template and social media templates:** These templates are designed for use on social media channels (e.g. X cards). Additionally, the quote card templates can be used to highlight key messages.
- **Newsletter:** A template has been designed to facilitate the creation of external newsletters.

Further templates will be developed and added as required over the duration of the project. This includes designing templates for scientific posters, which will be used at conferences and events to present research findings and project updates in a visually appealing and consistent manner.

2.4.3 Information sheet, banner and other materials

To support communications with external audiences, and summarising the key messages of AD-RIDDLE, we have developed an initial information sheet (Fig.4, complete with an AD-RIDDLE infographic (Fig. 5) designed in line with the project's visual identity. An AD-RIDDLE roll-up banner has also been produced, together with AD-RIDDLE business cards that can be easily distributed at conferences and other events (Fig. 4). It was designed to enhance the visibility of the AD-RIDDLE project and ensure a strong visual presence at conferences, exhibitions and other public

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engagements. It could also serve as a point of interest at exhibition booths to attract attention and convey key messages about the project, complemented by the information sheet and business cards for wider dissemination and sharing.

Finally, to support presentations of AD-RIDDLE by project partners, we have developed a short summary slide deck (Fig. 6 below), and we are in the process of creating a full-length pitch deck. These materials will be updated as required, as the project progresses, and serve as a basis for the development of further communication materials tailored to specific audiences (e.g. study participants).

Fig.4 (L-R) AD-Riddle printed materials: roll-up banner, business cards, info sheet

Fig. 5 (below). AD-RIDDLE infographic

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Fig.6. Short AD-RIDDLE slide deck

Alzheimer's Disease – Real-world Implementation, Deployment and Validation of Early Detection Tools and Lifestyle Enhancement

The AD-RIDDLE project is creating a modular toolbox platform to enhance the detection, diagnosis, prevention and treatment of Alzheimer's disease.

The AD-RIDDLE toolbox platform will equip healthcare providers with validated technologies, tools and biomarkers, enabling them to make the best choices for their patients.

Scan the QR code to visit the AD-RIDDLE website & channels!

The AD-RIDDLE toolbox platform will include:

- A modular digital engagement portal with self-assessment tools and resources for patients, caregivers, and the public
- Accessible, validated screening tools, including digital cognitive assessments and blood-based biomarker tests
- A decision support kit with validated algorithms for clinical decisions
- Personalised therapeutic protocols, matching patients with pharmacological and/or lifestyle interventions using a precision prevention approach

ABOUT US

Collaborating to advance Alzheimer's research and care

The AD-RIDDLE consortium unites public and private sector partners, including healthcare providers, research institutions, technology developers, and patient organisations.

24 partner organisations
Academia, healthcare, industry, SMEs and non-profit organisations

Eleven countries
Partners located in countries across Europe, and the US

Five years
Support from the EU's Innovative Health Initiative, 2024 - 2029

ACADEMIA & HEALTHCARE

INDUSTRY & SMEs

NON-PROFIT ORGANISATIONS

2.4.4 Website

The AD-RIDDLE website is a **key channel** for external outreach, communication and dissemination, serving as a central hub for all project-related information and activities. The website can be accessed at <https://ad-riddle.org/>. The first version of the AD-RIDDLE website is structured around three pages:

- **Homepage:** provides an overview of the project and explains the challenge being addressed by AD-RIDDLE (Fig. 7)
- **About:** list the different partners making the AD-RIDDLE consortium and give the opportunity to the visitors to subscribe to the project's newsletter
- **News and Resources:** includes articles providing updates on the project. This section also serves as a repository for resources.

The website will be progressively updated throughout the project to reflect new content and respond to the changing needs of the project and its stakeholders. Planned updates include:

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- **Content enrichment:** Adding detailed information on the project's progress and achievements
- **Expanded News and Resources section:** Including interviews with project members, publications and public deliverables
- **Structural enhancements:** Adjusting the website structure to better serve stakeholder needs as the project evolves.

By maintaining a dynamic and user-friendly website, AD-RIDDLE aims to:

- **Ensure effective communication:** Inform a broad audience about the AD-RIDDLE project and its goals
- **Foster engagement:** Keep stakeholders engaged through tailored content and updates
- **Facilitate dissemination:** Ensure the effective dissemination of project outputs
- **Promote events:** Provide information about AD-RIDDLE events.

Fig. 7: Homepage of the AD-RIDDLE website

2.4.5 Social media channels

Social media platforms enable connections between millions of users worldwide. The presence of AD-RIDDLE on social media is essential for increasing **project visibility** and for reaching a broad and diverse audience, including researchers, clinicians, policymakers and the general public. Currently, AD-RIDDLE uses the most popular social networks with a presence on X (formerly Twitter) ([@AD_RIDDLE](#)) and [LinkedIn](#), with over 650 followers in total (Fig.8).

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Fig. 8: AD-RIDDLE X handle and LinkedIn page

To ensure a **consistent and impactful presence** on social media, specific messages about the AD-RIDDLE project will be posted on a regular basis. The messages will be adapted across social media channels to maximise reach and engagement.

Partners will be encouraged to share and amplify the messages posted on the AD-RIDDLE social media channels through their networks, further extending the reach and impact.

An implementation calendar will be prepared quarterly to plan the social media posts. Messages will be prepared in advance, ensuring they are ready for timely posting. Visuals, hashtags and links to additional resources (also driving traffic to the project website) will be included to enhance engagement. Some posts will be scheduled using social media management tools to ensure timely delivery and consistency.

To maximise the impact of our communication efforts, specific messages about the AD-RIDDLE project will be strategically timed to coincide with awareness days and other high-profile points in the calendar (e.g. key events). This approach will increase public awareness of the project and facilitate the dissemination of major outputs. As an example, scientific publications and participation at conferences will be highlighted via social media. The table below outlines key dates of awareness days where targeted messaging could be deployed.

Awareness Days	Dates	Message focus
International Day of Girls & Women In Science	11 February	Highlighting women researchers in AD-RIDDLE
International Women's Day	8 March	Highlighting women researchers in AD-RIDDLE
Brain Awareness Week	Mid-March	Importance of early detection and prevention in Alzheimer's disease
Europe Day	9 May	Highlighting European collaboration in AD-RIDDLE
World Brain Day	22 July	Link between mental health and Alzheimer's
World Alzheimer's Month	September	Major project updates and research findings
World Alzheimer's Day	21 September	Importance of AD-RIDDLE for cross-sector progress in Alzheimer's disease research and care
World Mental Health Day	10 October	Link between mental health and Alzheimer's disease

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In addition to X and LinkedIn, we are also investigating the use of other social media channels such as **Facebook** to foster community engagement and **YouTube** to share interviews with key stakeholders and provide a repository of recorded events.

2.4.6 Newsletters

AD-RIDDLE will develop a quarterly newsletter for dissemination to external audiences. The newsletter will be disseminated to subscribers and will act as a channel for highlighting success stories, partner features, and event announcements. More specific sends could be used to disseminate particular messages and drive specific actions.

The first external newsletter for wider audiences will be launched in January 2025, to celebrate the first year of AD-RIDDLE. Audiences can subscribe to the newsletter via a signup form embedded on the AD-RIDDLE website. The newsletter will be created using MailChimp and will include a welcome letter from AD-RIDDLE co-Leads, a spotlight on major project update(s), featured articles and partner interviews, as well as a calendar of upcoming events.

2.4.7 Press releases

Press releases will be used to highlight major achievements and milestones for AD-RIDDLE, and will be disseminated via the AD-RIDDLE social media channels and the project website. AD-RIDDLE will also leverage the communication channels and networks of project partners to achieve wider dissemination. Where relevant, press releases will be shared with platforms such as [ScienceX](#) and [EurekAlert!](#), enabling outreach to science media, journalists and the general public.

The first AD-RIDDLE press release was issued upon project launch, in January 2024. It was issued on EurekAlert! and was also shared via ScienceX, and the websites and social media channels of several project partners (illustrated in Fig. 9 below). The EurekAlert! press release can be found here: <https://www.eurekalert.org/news-releases/1032693>

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Fig. 9: Dissemination of AD-RIDDLE press release by project partners

2.4.8 Conference and events

Participation in conferences and events is an **important channel** for the dissemination of AD-RIDDLE achievements to a wide range of audiences. This will constitute a key action to make a significant impact, notably within the scientific and clinical communities. Engaging in these events will provide opportunities to raise awareness about the project and disseminate its outputs and findings effectively.

The AD-RIDDLE consortium will be actively encouraged to regularly attend key international and national events (i.e. AD/PD, AAIC, Alzheimer Europe conference, ADI conference, DAC Learning Laboratory). Every opportunity will be taken to present AD-RIDDLE either in the form of oral talks, posters or distributing AD-RIDDLE printed materials. This multi-faceted approach ensures comprehensive coverage and engagement with stakeholders. By participating in these key events and leveraging each opportunity for dissemination, AD-RIDDLE aims to enhance its visibility and foster collaborations.

A list of international conferences where the project could be presented will be developed and updated on a regular basis. This calendar will be accessible to the consortium through the internal SharePoint platform, ensuring that all members are aware of and can plan for participation in these events. The key events for 2024 are shown in the table below.

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Conference	Date	Audience reached
International Conference on Alzheimer's and Parkinson's Diseases and related neurological disorders (AD/PD)	5-9 March	Medical and scientific professionals
Global Conference of Alzheimer's Disease International (ADI)	24-26 April	Scientific care and medical professionals; people with dementia, carers, Alzheimer associations
Alzheimer's Association International Conference (AAIC)	28 July – 1 August	Medical and scientific professionals
Alzheimer Europe Conference (AEC)	8-10 October	People with dementia, carers, Alzheimer associations, policy makers, health and social care professionals, researchers and industry representatives
Clinical Trials on Alzheimer's Disease conference (CTAD)	29 October – 1 November	Medical and scientific professionals

As an example, Project co-lead Miia Kivipelto attended the AD/PD2024 conference in Lisbon and was invited to join the symposium organised by the Alzheimer's Disease Data Initiative (ADDI), titled "How several key efforts are making their data and samples accessible to the broader research community. She took this opportunity to highlight AD-RIDDLE, stating *"We're trying to solve the riddle of #Alzheimers disease and narrow the implementation gap, so patients can access the right interventions at the right time. AD-RIDDLE has 24 partners, and together we are creating a flexible toolbox platform - to offer solutions to challenges across the entire clinical pathway"*.

AD-RIDDLE will also explore the possibility of organising sponsored symposia, booths or workshops and will leverage on partner's communication channels.

Tracking attendance at events is crucial for maximising the project's visibility and impact. A dissemination tracker (see section 2.6.2) has been developed to monitor participation and build a robust social media presence.

2.4.9 Leveraging AE channels

Policymakers and the wider **dementia community**, including Alzheimer's associations, research participants, people with Alzheimer's disease and carers, represent a key audience for the AD-RIDDLE Project. AD-RIDDLE partner Alzheimer Europe will use its extensive network of 41 member associations from 36 countries, along with its established communication tools, to effectively reach these audiences. By leveraging Alzheimer Europe's communication channels, AD-RIDDLE will ensure that its progress and findings reach a wide audience, ultimately enhancing the project's impact.

- **Website and newsletter:** Alzheimer Europe's website and the monthly Alzheimer Europe newsletter (> 10,000 subscribers) will feature regular updates about AD-RIDDLE, highlighting key achievements and significant milestones.

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- **Social Media Channels:** AD-RIDDLE updates will be shared through Alzheimer Europe’s social media platforms, including [X](#) (formerly Twitter; >14k followers), [LinkedIn](#) (>5k followers), [Facebook](#) and [Instagram](#).
- **Magazine:** The "Dementia in Europe" magazine, sent to all Members of the European Parliament and many policymakers at the European Commission, World Health Organization, and other governmental bodies, will feature articles on AD-RIDDLE.
- **Meetings:** AD-RIDDLE will be discussed at meetings with national Alzheimer’s associations and during European Parliament lunch debates. AD-RIDDLE members will have the opportunity to submit abstracts annually to the Alzheimer Europe conference (the 2023 edition attracted over 1,000 delegates).

AD-RIDDLE has already been featured in the June 2024 issue of "Dementia in Europe" magazine, with an interview piece featuring the project leads, Miia Kivipelto and Niranjana Bose. Additionally, the AD-RIDDLE press release announcing the launch of the project has been featured on the Alzheimer Europe website, included in the newsletter and shared via its social media channels.

2.4.10 Leveraging ADI channels

Similarly, AD-RIDDLE partner Alzheimer’s Disease International (ADI) will leverage its network of 105 Alzheimer and dementia organisations around the world, many of which overlap with the membership of Alzheimer Europe. ADI also interacts with global policymakers, extending the reach of AD-RIDDLE to international partners beyond Europe, further enhancing the impact of the project.

- **Website:** News items about AD-RIDDLE will be published on the ADI website, highlighting key achievements and significant milestones
- **Social Media Channels:** AD-RIDDLE updates will be shared through ADI’s social media platforms, including [X](#), [LinkedIn](#), [Facebook](#) and [Instagram](#). ADI has a substantial following on all these channels (e.g. Facebook: 23.4K followers)
- **Meetings:** AD-RIDDLE will be discussed at meetings with national Alzheimer’s associations, as well as the Biennial Global Conference of ADI, the last edition of which attracted over 1,000 delegates to the beautiful city of Krakow.
- **ADI Advisory Panels:** ADI will share updates and outputs with their Medical and Scientific Advisory Panel and their Global Dementia Expert Panel.
- **ADI Publications:** When possible, ADI can feature AD-RIDDLE in key global publications. For example, ADI featured a key article from Miia Kivipelto and Niranjana Bose outlining the potential of the AD-RIDDLE in the From Plan to Impact VII Report launched at the World

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Health Assembly in May 2024. In addition, ADI features regular updates in their Global Perspectives newsletter.

An update on AD-RIDDLE was featured on the ADI website following the kick-off meeting in June 2024. AD-RIDDLE was also highlighted by ADI at the Dialogues in Neurodegenerative Disorders conference, organised in Ljubljana, Slovenia.

2.4.11 Internal platform

While all the above materials and tools are crucial for facilitating external communication, efficient collaboration and effective **internal communication** are also strategic priorities for the AD-RIDDLE consortium (internal communication is led by WP9). To support these objectives, SharePoint will be used as an internal platform, providing each partner with independent access to essential documents and resources, including meeting minutes, agendas, deliverables, mailing lists, templates, logo and key supporting materials. By providing a centralised and secure location for all project-related materials, SharePoint enhances the efficiency of internal communication and collaboration. WP9 has also developed an internal newsletter to support consortium engagement, which will be published on a quarterly basis.

2.5 Communication activities

This section of the communication and dissemination plan maps out the activities that will be used to engage and communicate with the audiences identified above, disseminating key messages for AD-RIDDLE using communication tools and channels. It includes a proposed timescale for key activities, mapped to project milestones and anticipated outputs.

The table below contains a non-exhaustive list of the communication tools and channels that will be leveraged to achieve the different communication goals of AD-RIDDLE, identifying the target audiences for the communication activities.

Communication goal	Key audiences	Tools & Channels
Build Awareness	Clinicians	Visual identity
<i>Creating a clear identity for AD-RIDDLE, raising awareness of the project across stakeholder groups and audiences</i>	Memory clinics & primary care	Templates
	Patients and people at risk of AD	Information sheets & cards
	Caregivers	Roll-up banner
	Technology & test developers	Pitch deck
	AD researchers	
	Professional societies	Social media
	Patient organisations	Website
	Industry	Scientific conferences
	Healthcare systems	AE & ADI conferences
	HTA & Payers	Public awareness campaigns
	Policymakers	
	Research funders	
	Science media & journalists	
General public		

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<p>Generate Interest</p> <p><i>Generating interest in AD-RIDDLE from key stakeholders, including potential end-users of the AD-RIDDLE toolbox platform, as well as gatekeepers to these communities</i></p>	<p>Clinicians Memory clinics & primary care Patients and people at risk of AD Caregivers Technology & test developers Healthcare systems Professional societies Patient organisations Science media & journalists</p>	<p>Newsletters & mailers Information sheets and other materials Pitch deck Social media Press releases Scientific conferences AE & ADI conferences Public awareness campaigns</p>
<p>Educate & share knowledge</p> <p><i>Disseminating project findings and knowledge to key stakeholders, advancing research and positioning AD-RIDDLE as a validated platform to advance AD detection, diagnosis and treatment</i></p>	<p>Clinicians Memory clinics & primary care Patients and people at risk of AD Caregivers Technology & test developers AD researchers Healthcare systems HTA & Payers Policymakers</p>	<p>Newsletters & mailers Information sheets and other materials Pitch deck Social media Website Press releases Scientific publications Scientific conferences AE & ADI conferences Public awareness campaigns</p>
<p>Motivate engagement</p> <p><i>Build an engaged community around AD-RIDDLE to ensure interest and support at platform launch; enhancing sustainability and paving the way for wider adoption</i></p>	<p>Clinicians Memory clinics & primary care Patients and people at risk of AD Caregivers Technology & test developers AD researchers Professional societies Patient organisations Healthcare systems HTA & Payers Policymakers Industry</p>	<p>Newsletters & mailers Social media Press releases Scientific conferences AE & ADI conferences Other meetings and events</p>
<p>Create impact</p> <p><i>Influence healthcare systems and policy, leading to positive changes in clinical practice with long-term benefits and societal impacts</i></p>	<p>Healthcare systems Policymakers HTA & payers Professional societies Patient organisations Industry</p>	<p>Newsletters & mailers Website Press releases Scientific publications AE & ADI conferences Policy meetings and events Public awareness campaigns</p>

2.5.1 IHI and UKRI communication guidelines

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AD-RIDDLE is an IHI-funded project and must adhere to the **IHI communication guidelines**. The project grant agreement details the rules for communication activities. All project partners are expected to familiarise themselves with these rules and ensure compliance in their communication efforts. For more detailed information, please refer to the article 17 (Communication, Dissemination and Visibility) in Annex 1.

All project communication activities, including media relations, conferences, seminars, information material (brochures, leaflets, posters, presentations, etc.), and dissemination activities in electronic form, via traditional or social media, must acknowledge IHI support. This also applies to any infrastructure, equipment, vehicles, supplies, or major results funded by the grant. The requirements include:

- **Funding Acknowledgement:** All communications must include a statement acknowledging IHI funding.

“This project is supported by the Innovative Health Initiative Joint Undertaking (IHI JU) under grant agreement No. 101132933. The JU receives support from the European Union’s Horizon Europe research and innovation programme and COCIR, EFPIA, EuropaBio, MedTech Europe and Vaccines Europe, with Davos Alzheimer’s Collaborative, Combinostics OY., Cambridge Cognition Ltd., C2N Diagnostics LLC, and neotiv GmbH.”

- **Disclaimer:** Communications must include a disclaimer.

“Funded by the European Union, the private members, UKRI, and the contributing partners of the IHI JU. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the aforementioned parties. None of the aforementioned parties can be held responsible for them.”

- **Logos:** the IHI JU logo, the EU emblem accompanied by the words Co-funded by the European Union, the logos of COCIR, EFPIA, EuropaBio, MedTech Europe, and Vaccines Europe.

In the case of dissemination of results, the IHI guidelines state that the results of the project must be disseminated promptly and in a publicly accessible format, subject to restrictions due to the protection of intellectual property, security rules, or legitimate interests. Beneficiaries intending to disseminate their results must provide at least 15 days' advance notice to other beneficiaries, unless agreed otherwise. This notice should include sufficient information about the results to be disseminated. Additionally, open-access must be provided for peer-reviewed scientific publications.

Acknowledging UK Research and Innovation

Funding for UK-based AD-RIDDLE partners (University of Leicester, NICE, and Imperial College London) is provided via the Horizon Europe guarantee scheme, by UK Research and Innovation (UKRI). According to the guarantee scheme [guidelines](#), AD-RIDDLE must also acknowledge funding received from UKRI in its research publications.

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This includes, but is not limited to:

- research articles published in journals
- conference proceedings and publication platforms
- monographs
- book chapters
- edited collections
- outputs deposited at institutional or subject repositories.

As AD-RIDDLE is a consortium project, each UK partner has grant reference numbers that should be cited using the following wording:

- This work was funded by UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) under the UK government’s Horizon Europe funding guarantee [grant number xxxx].’

2.5.2 Initial communication roadmap

To raise awareness and understanding of AD-RIDDLE among target audiences, we plan to disseminate the achievement of key milestones and deliverables. This will be achieved through coordinated dissemination activities via the project’s website and social media channels. To ensure these communications are well-planned and timely, an initial communication roadmap outlining important milestones and deliverables has been developed in the table below. By following this communication roadmap, AD-RIDDLE aims to effectively engage stakeholders and disseminate important project outcomes, ensuring that the project's impact is maximised throughout its duration.

Date	Deliverable (month)	Message
D7.1	Review on ethics of dementia risk (M12)	<i>AD-RIDDLE is advancing dementia risk reduction in an ethical, patient-centered way</i>
D3.1	Study initiation package: BBMs Core protocol with sub-studies (M12)	<i>The AD-RIDDLE platform components are evidence-based, validated tools enabling AD detection and diagnosis</i>
D2.2	Study initiation package: core protocol with all sub-studies for digital cognitive assessments (M18)	<i>The AD-RIDDLE platform components are evidence-based, validated tools enabling AD detection and diagnosis</i>
D4.1	Development of predictive algorithms (M18)	<i>AD-RIDDLE is building on the latest technological advances to identify people at risk of AD, and match patients with the right interventions, and the right time.</i>
D7.2	Policy review on dementia risk reduction (M24)	<i>AD-RIDDLE is informed by the latest policy analyses, working towards equitable</i>

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		<i>access to risk reduction measures across Europe</i>
D1.3	Beta digital engagement portal (M24)	<i>AD-RIDDLE provides tangible options to help people understand and manage their cognitive health</i>
D7.3	Literature review of funding models (M24)	<i>AD-RIDDLE is guided by experts on health economics, paving the way for sustainable implementation and access</i>
D7.6	Decision Tool (M36)	<i>AD-RIDDLE supports healthcare providers and clinicians to make the best choices for their patients in an evidence-based way</i>
D2.5	Report on status of posting results, including the screening performance of digital cognitive tools, and implementation guidelines (M60)	<i>AD-RIDDLE is unlocking efficiencies for AD detection and diagnosis, using tests validated in the real-world setting</i>
D3.4	BBMs impact in real-world settings (M60)	<i>AD-RIDDLE is unlocking efficiencies for AD detection and diagnosis, using tests validated in the real-world setting</i>
D4.4	Decision support toolkit (M60)	<i>AD-RIDDLE supports healthcare providers and clinicians to make the best choices for their patients in an evidence-based way</i>
D9.12	Final Data Management Plan (M60)	<i>AD-RIDDLE effectively manages the security, privacy and governance of patient datasets</i>

2.5.3 Scientific dissemination

Scientific dissemination is a crucial component of the AD-RIDDLE project, aimed at sharing research findings and achievements with the scientific community (i.e., researchers, clinicians). To achieve the project objectives, the AD-RIDDLE project will engage in the following scientific dissemination activities:

- **Scientific publications**
 - Publish research findings in high-impact and peer-reviewed journals.
 - Ensure open access to publications where possible to maximize reach and impact (as required by the IHI Grant Agreement) and where possible will be made widely available via the AD-RIDDLE website and/or research repositories such as Zenodo.
- **Attendance at scientific conferences and workshops**
 - Participation in conferences will constitute a key action in our dissemination strategy. The AD-RIDDLE partners are committed to participating in national/international events, including conferences, digital exhibitions, international forums and scientific

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symposia, to showcase the project results. This will include oral presentations, poster sessions, and panel discussions (see section 2.4.8).

- Organise symposia or special sessions at major conferences to highlight AD-RIDDLE’s work and facilitate discussions on key topics.
- Collaborate with other research initiatives and institutions to host joint events that promote knowledge exchange and interdisciplinary collaboration.

- **Reports**

- Develop comprehensive reports on key findings and recommendations. These documents will be aimed at both the scientific community and policymakers, providing in-depth analysis and actionable insights. As an example, outreach efforts will be dedicated to communicate and disseminate policy briefs and summaries developed by WP5.

A first, Open Access scientific article for AD-RIDDLE was published in the Journal of Prevention of Alzheimer’s Disease (JPAD) on 30 January, on the same day as the press release highlighting the project launch. The article is entitled “Validation, deployment, and real-world implementation of a modular toolbox for Alzheimer’s Disease detection and dementia risk reduction: the AD-RIDDLE project (Malzbender K, et al, 2024) and can be accessed here:

<https://link.springer.com/article/10.14283/jpad.2024.32>.

2.5.4 Public awareness campaigns

Awareness plays a crucial role in encouraging healthy habits and healthcare-seeking behaviours. Increasing awareness is the first step towards informed decision-making, enabling individuals to actively participate in their own care. AD-RIDDLE partners, led by Alzheimer Europe, Alzheimer’s Disease International, Fingers Brain Health Institute and Davos Alzheimer’s Collaborative, will develop a Public Awareness Strategy (D8.3) in collaboration with the project’s Patient and Public Advisory Group (comprising people with or at risk of AD), national Alzheimer’s Associations, and healthcare professionals.

This strategy will be used to organise two awareness campaigns (in Year 2 and Year 4 of AD-RIDDLE) to increase awareness of positive brain health and dementia prevention practices, and support implementation and adoption of the AD-RIDDLE toolbox platform. These campaigns will use dementia-inclusive messaging to promote positive engagement with brain health, and reduce the stigma around cognitive impairment, with a focus on how AD-RIDDLE and similar programs can help in the Y4 campaign. Integrating input from key stakeholders from the PPAG, campaigns will be carefully designed to ensure they use the right language and imagery to reach minority, deprived, and socially excluded groups, which are often at highest risk of developing AD and dementia. Together, these campaigns will increase awareness of, engagement with, and implementation of AD-RIDDLE, also demonstrating the added value of public-private collaboration to address important societal challenges.

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2.6 Indicators, monitoring and evaluation

2.6.1 Indicators

Measuring the success of communication is crucial for ensuring the effectiveness of the communication and dissemination strategy. This communication plan will be adaptable, based on the results obtained from the key communication performance indicators.

These indicators are metrics that provide quantitative or qualitative information of the audience response to communication activities. By regularly tracking and analysing these metrics, AD-RIDDLE will ensure that its communication activities are effective and aligned with the project's goals. These metrics will help the consortium evaluate and adjust if needed communication efforts in terms of visibility and awareness of the project.

The communication indicators to be collected by AD-RIDDLE are detailed in the table below. This will be regularly revisited and updated to reflect changes and improvements in the communication plan.

Tool & Material	Quantitative indicator and data source	Frequency	Target
Project website	Number of visitors, page views and session duration (Matomo Analytics)	Monthly	Awareness Increased number over time
Social media (X, LinkedIn)	Number of followers, likes, shares and impressions (X, LinkedIn Analytics)	Monthly	Awareness and engagement Increased number over time
Newsletter	Number of subscribers, open rates, clicks and downloads (MailChimp Analytics)	Quarterly	Engagement Growth in subscriptions over time
Events & conferences	Number of talk & poster presentations, type of event and number of attendees	Per event	Awareness and uptake
Publications	Number of publications, downloads and impact factor	Per publication	Awareness and uptake
Communication materials	Number of times project materials are downloaded or distributed	Yearly	Awareness, engagement and uptake
Press and media coverage	Number of articles/appearances in media and type of articles	Yearly	Awareness and uptake

In addition to quantitative metrics, qualitative indicators will also be used to evaluate the communication efforts and provide further insights into the audience's perceptions, which are not always captured by quantitative measures alone. These qualitative indicators will complement the quantitative metrics, offering a holistic view of the communication strategy's effectiveness. Qualitative indicators will include stakeholder feedback, testimonials and focus groups among others.

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2.6.2 Tracker

To effectively monitor and record communication activities, AD-RIDDLE has developed a **self-monitoring tool**, stored on the internal SharePoint platform. This tracker will facilitate the collection of detailed information regarding communication activities, such as the type of activity, date and audience reached. This tracker is essential for supporting periodic reporting of communication activities to IHI, as required in the Grant Agreement. All partners will be regularly asked to check the list of reported dissemination activities and update/correct the information contained therein.

The tracker will also include details of participation at conferences, capturing information such as event name, date, name of the presenter and type of presentation. This listing will assist in planning and advertising communication activities on social media channels, enhancing the visibility of AD-RIDDLE.

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ANNEXES

Annex 1 - COMMUNICATION, DISSEMINATION, OPEN SCIENCE AND VISIBILITY (— ARTICLE 17)

Dissemination

Dissemination of results

The beneficiaries must disseminate their results as soon as feasible, in a publicly available format, subject to any restrictions due to the protection of intellectual property, security rules or legitimate interests.

A beneficiary that intends to disseminate its results must give at least 15 days advance notice to the other beneficiaries (unless agreed otherwise), together with sufficient information on the results it will disseminate.

Any other beneficiary may object within (unless agreed otherwise) 15 days of receiving notification, if it can show that its legitimate interests in relation to the results or background would be significantly harmed. In such cases, the results may not be disseminated unless appropriate steps are taken to safeguard those interests.

Additional dissemination obligations

Where the call conditions impose additional dissemination obligations, the beneficiaries must also comply with those.

Open Science

Open science: open access to scientific publications

The beneficiaries must ensure open access to peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to their results. In particular, they must ensure that:

- at the latest at the time of publication, a machine-readable electronic copy of the published version or the final peer-reviewed manuscript accepted for publication, is deposited in a trusted repository for scientific publications
- immediate open access is provided to the deposited publication via the repository, under the latest available version of the Creative Commons Attribution International Public Licence (CC BY) or a licence with equivalent rights; for monographs and other long-text formats, the licence may exclude commercial uses and derivative works (e.g. CC BY-NC, CC BY-ND) and
- information is given via the repository about any research output or any other tools and instruments needed to validate the conclusions of the scientific publication.

Beneficiaries (or authors) must retain sufficient intellectual property rights to comply with the

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open access requirements.

Metadata of deposited publications must be open under a Creative Common Public Domain Dedication (CC 0) or equivalent, in line with the FAIR principles (in particular machineactionable) and provide information at least about the following: publication (author(s), title, date of publication, publication venue); Horizon Europe or Euratom funding; grant project name, acronym and number; licensing terms; persistent identifiers for the publication, the authors involved in the action and, if possible, for their organisations and the grant. Where applicable, the metadata must include persistent identifiers for any research output or any other tools and instruments needed to validate the conclusions of the publication.

Only publication fees in full open access venues for peer-reviewed scientific publications are eligible for reimbursement.

Open science: research data management

The beneficiaries must manage the digital research data generated in the action ('data') responsibly, in line with the FAIR principles and by taking all of the following actions:

- establish a data management plan ('DMP') (and regularly update it)
- as soon as possible and within the deadlines set out in the DMP, deposit the data in a trusted repository; if required in the call conditions, this repository must be federated in the EOSC in compliance with EOSC requirements
- as soon as possible and within the deadlines set out in the DMP, ensure open access — via the repository — to the deposited data, under the latest available version of the Creative Commons Attribution International Public License (CC BY) or Creative Commons Public Domain Dedication (CC 0) or a licence with equivalent rights, following the principle 'as open as possible as closed as necessary', unless providing open access would in particular:
 - be against the beneficiary's legitimate interests, including regarding commercial exploitation, or
 - be contrary to any other constraints, in particular the EU competitive interests or the beneficiary's obligations under this Agreement; if open access is not provided (to some or all data), this must be justified in the DMP
- provide information via the repository about any research output or any other tools and instruments needed to re-use or validate the data.

Metadata of deposited data must be open under a Creative Common Public Domain Dedication (CC 0) or equivalent (to the extent legitimate interests or constraints are safeguarded), in line with the FAIR principles (in particular machine-actionable) and provide information at least about the following: datasets (description, date of deposit, author(s), venue and embargo); Horizon Europe or Euratom funding; grant project name, acronym and number; licensing terms; persistent identifiers for the dataset, the authors involved in the action, and, if possible, for their organisations and the grant. Where applicable, the metadata must include persistent identifiers for related publications and other research outputs.

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Open science: additional practices

Where the call conditions impose additional obligations regarding open science practices, the beneficiaries must also comply with those.

Where the call conditions impose additional obligations regarding the validation of scientific publications, the beneficiaries must provide (digital or physical) access to data or other results needed for validation of the conclusions of scientific publications, to the extent that their legitimate interests or constraints are safeguarded (and unless they already provided the (open) access at publication).

Where the call conditions impose additional open science obligations in case of a public emergency, the beneficiaries must (if requested by the granting authority) immediately deposit any research output in a repository and provide open access to it under a CC BY licence, a Public Domain Dedication (CC 0) or equivalent. As an exception, if the access would be against the beneficiaries' legitimate interests, the beneficiaries must grant nonexclusive licenses — under fair and reasonable conditions — to legal entities that need the research output to address the public emergency and commit to rapidly and broadly exploit the resulting products and services at fair and reasonable conditions. This provision applies up to four years after the end of the action (see Data Sheet, Point 1).

Plan for the exploitation and dissemination of results including communication activities

Unless excluded by the call conditions, the beneficiaries must provide and regularly update a plan for the exploitation and dissemination of results including communication activities.